

Supplementary Material for An innovative filler manipulation approach for low-cost composite coatings on metallic PEMFC Bipolar Plates

S1 - On the impact of coating thickness on ICR:

The impact of coating thickness on the ICR of aligned samples was investigated, and the results are shown in Figure S1.

Figure S1. The impact of the coating thickness on the interfacial contact resistance, for aligned samples.

In this case, the thinner coatings have a lower ICR than the thicker coatings. A low ICR is dependent on achieving particle-to-particle contact during the alignment process, and for the thinner coatings, this is easier due to the smaller number of particles needed to connect to form a conductive pathway through the coating.

S2 – Additional in-situ testing of baseline bipolar plates with Au coated stainless steel and uncoated stainless steel.

PEM FC with gold-plated endplates on both the anode and the cathode exhibited very good performance according to load curves. This was further supported by EIS spectra, included in Figure S2.

Figure S2. EIS of single PEM fuel cell with Au-plated stainless-steel endplates obtained after different times of cell operation at voltage of 0.5 V (C). Evaluated values of high-frequency Ohmic resistance and total polarisation resistance are included in plot inset (D), as well as optical camera images of the surface of the anodic endplate before (A) and after (B) test.

EIS spectra exhibited small decrease of Ohmic and polarisation resistance during the time of the operation, most probably connected to progressive activation of the MEA. In this case, it is evident that the Ohmic resistance of the endplates, as shown from the ICR values, did not represent a significant part of the total Ohmic resistance of the cell, concluding that no passivation or dissolution of endplates occurred. Therefore, it can be considered that the Ohmic resistance of MEA and SS316L is between 30 and 40 $m\Omega$ during the entire duration of the experiment. Not surprisingly, no significant changes on the surface of the anodic endplate were observed after the experiment.

EIS spectra of the PEM FC with SS316L endplates on both the anode and cathode exhibited a relatively stable shape during the entire duration of the experiment, as seen in Figure S3. During operation, the Ohmic resistance of the cell was initially 75 % higher than the single cell with gold plating. Both the Ohmic and polarisation resistance progressively increased during the experiment, though only by a small margin. This suggests that the SS316L endplates were already covered by thin passivation layer. This was expected, as endplates were only purified by acetone for degreasing and rinsed in ultrasound and deionised water. The shape of the spectra indicates an additional time constant, more pronounced when compared to the gold plated samples. This behaviour may be understood by comparing to the ex-situ testing. Here the blank stainless steel plate shows order of magnitude higher current densities in the potential region of 0.1 V vs. SHE. The steel surface is therefore clearly not well protected under the operational conditions of the fuel cell. In terms of surface changes, oxidised spots were observed

after the experiment on the anode. This was caused by the partial dissolution of the endplate in hotspots. This affected also the value of the ICR of the anode, determined ex situ.

Figure S3. Electrochemical impedance spectra of single PEM fuel cell with stainless-steel endplates obtained after different times of cell operation at voltage of 0.5 V (C). Evaluated values of high-frequency Ohmic resistance and total polarisation resistance are included in plot inset (D), as well as optical camera images of the surface of the cathodic endplate before (A) and after (B) test.

For the sample with uncoated SS316L on the cathode and the Au-plated on the anode, both the Ohmic and polarisation resistance of the cell exhibited steady increase during the operation, most probably due to degradation of the SS316L endplate, as seen in Figure S4.

Figure S4. Electrochemical impedance spectra of single PEM fuel cell with Au-plated stainless-steel endplate on the anode and SS316L on the cathode obtained after different times of cell operation at voltage of 0.5 V (C). Evaluated values of high-frequency Ohmic resistance and total polarisation resistance are included in plot inset (D), as well as optical camera images of surface of anodic endplate before (A) and after (B) test.

In this case, both the passivation of the SS316L and its possible partial dissolution led to the increase in the Ohmic resistance and the poisoning of ionomer in catalyst layer, respectively. This can be observed as a simultaneous increase of the Ohmic and polarisation resistance during the PEMFC operation.